

LEADSx2030
ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS

ADVANCED DIGITAL SKILLS STATE-OF-PLAY REPORT

Overview of demand and supply of digital talent in the EU

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report provides a critical review of the Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) landscape in the EU-27, framing challenges against the Digital Decade Policy Programme (DDPP) 2030 objectives. The DDPP 2030 sets an ambitious headline target of 20 million ICT specialists employed across the EU.

The Key Challenge: Current projections indicate a persistent and substantial shortfall. If present trends continue, the EU will reach only 12.2 million ICT professionals by 2030, leaving a gap of 7.8 million specialists below the DDPP goal. This shortage acts as a brake on economic growth and risks undermining Europe's leadership in critical fields such as AI.

A snapshot of ADS supply and demand

While the EU is a global powerhouse for ICT roles, currently employing over 10.3 million ICT Specialists (second only to Chinese estimates), the current growth rate falls behind what is required by 5.5 percentage points annually. By 2035, the net growth required for ICT Professionals and ICT Technicians is 1.7 million individuals. Accounting for replacement (due to retirement or change of occupation), a total of 4.2 million new entrants must be trained or recruited.

Although the EU performs well in the overall proportion of STEM graduates, it lags behind leaders like the US and UK in ICT-specific disciplines. In addition, the digital workforce suffers from a largely stagnant gender imbalance, with only 19.5% of ICT specialists being women in 2024.

Dynamic skills pockets in demand

The total estimated number of vacancies for ICT Specialists in 2025 across the EU-27 is 420,000 positions. Analysis of Online Job Advertisements (OJA) reveals rapid shifts in specific skill requirements:

- **Leading Areas:** On a relative basis, the highest demand is concentrated in Data Science and Cybersecurity profiles.
- **Cross-Technology Shift:** There is a clear, overarching trend toward the rise of security and data management skills pockets. Cloud Security experienced a significant rise of 18 places in ranking between 2023 and 2025.
- **AI Complexity:** The deployment of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is not a single profile. Successful adoption requires fundamental expertise in data management, cybersecurity, systems engineering, and general software.
- **Cloud Polarisation:** Distinct Cloud Computing roles are characterised by high polarisation, with Security Management surging by 282% and Network Security by 234% in growth.
- **Vendor Lock-in:** The ICT market shows centralisation, with AWS, Microsoft, and Google accounting for 70% of the EU market. A comparison of training programmes shows a significant presence of vendor-specific courses compared to generic/vendor-neutral offerings.

EU Strategic Investments

The European Union is actively addressing the supply gap through the Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) of the Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL). The SO4 Cluster is dedicated to developing Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) in key capacity areas (HPC, AI, Cybersecurity). The cluster comprises 55 initiatives (including specialized Master's courses, short-term training, and a Cybersecurity skills academy) focused on skills delivery between 2022 and 2029. **Financial Commitment:** The total combined investment (EU funding plus co-funding) for the SO4 actions amounts to €407 million.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ADS	Advanced Digital Skills
ADSEU	Advanced Digital Skills Cluster
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DDPP	Digital Decade Policy Programme
DIGITAL	Digital Europe Programme
EC	European Commission
EU-27	27 Member States of the European Union
GenAI	Generative AI
GVA	Gross Value Added
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HR	Human Resources
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
OJA	Open Jobs Advertisements
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
SO4	Strategic Objective 4 (Advanced Digital Skills) of the Digital Europe Programme
STEM	Science Technology Engineering Mathematics
VET	Vocational Education Training
WP	Work Package
CSA	Coordination and Support Action

1 Defining the need for more digital talent

1.1 Leading policy drivers

The Digital Decade Policy Programme (DDPP) 2030 sets out clear quantitative objectives for Advanced Digital Skills by 2030, with a **headline target of 20 million ICT specialists employed across the EU**, with a greater gender convergence. Based on the current trajectory, this will only be reached by 2051 and equally concerning is that over the past years negligible progress has been achieved in increasing the number of women in ICT occupations at 19.5% of the total.¹ The gap in digital talent (i.e. ICT Specialists) not only slows digital transformation but also acts as a brake on economic growth, productivity, and the pursuit of strategic autonomy.

The ambitions of the Digital Decade are complemented by the European Skills Agenda, renewed in 2025 with the launch of the Union of Skills initiative and the Skills Package. Built on the European competitiveness compass, its key objective is to close the digital skills gap in the EU, in cutting-edge domains like AI, Quantum, Virtual Worlds, and Semiconductors. Initiatives such as STEM Education Strategic Plan and the Unions of Skills focus on broadening participation and diversity in the STEM and ICT sectors.

This skills-driven transformation is closely linked to ability to execute on objectives of key strategic initiatives like the AI Continent Action Plan or the EU Chips Act. For example, the AI Continent Action Plan aims to make Europe a global leader in AI and includes among the seven pillar one on “Talent and Skills”. This pillar connects with both the Digital Decade and Skills Agenda, recognising that advanced digital literacy, cybersecurity expertise, and AI competence are vital for autonomy and resilience against threats such as disinformation, cyberattacks, and deepfakes.

1.2 Importance of the digital economy and the talent to power it

It is a common refrain from policy makers and industry leaders that we require greater access to talent with Advanced Digital Skills (ADS) as a means to secure our future competitiveness, and to regain a lost advantage in the digital sector. While the ICT sector may not be the biggest in the EU economy, it is the digitalisation of the whole economy that is to be a key driver of future growth. It was previously estimated that 70% of the future economic growth from 2022-2032 was to be digitally enabled.² What is more, this figure was published before the arrival of the ChatGPT moment of 2022.

The position for competitiveness and a resilient and enduring economy requires the mobilisation of large-scale investments, both in the tangible and intangible infrastructure, at core points of the digital value chain closing the gap with other global regions. The recent Draghi report estimated that 150B EUR investment is required annually from 2025-2030 to gain digital leadership with a further 100-150B EUR to deliver productivity breakthroughs³. The realisation of the value of such, as yet non-apparent, massive investments is dependent on the absorptive capacity of European companies, public bodies and researchers to translate capacity into capability.

It is readily believed that the divergent trend in productivity of the EU and US economies experienced since the turn of the century is due to the weaker or later ICT investments made by EU companies. This is further reinforced by the dependency for ICT capital on highly skilled talent and organisational transformation to realise productivity compared to previous capital investments.⁴ We must also understand that in the digital economy, that market dominance has a real impact on the employment and economies of other global regions. For example, recent estimates demonstrate that the purchase of US digital services (specifically

¹ COM(2025) 290 final

² World Economic Forum (2022)

³ For example, the EU Chips Act and InvestAI anticipate a funding provision of 11B EUR and 50B EUR respectively, resulting in a total mobilisation of 43 Bn EUR and 200Bn EUR in total for the period to 2030. As comparison, Google, Microsoft, Amazon and Meta together plan to invest 400Bn USD in AI in 2026.

⁴ The digital economy and the euro area (2020) ECB Economic Bulletin, Issue 8

cloud services) across the EU supports up to 1.9M US jobs and 1.1% of total US GDP (c. 323M USD annually).⁵

Currently the ICT Sector is one of the highest contributors of GVA per employment in the EU today. It possesses a ratio of 1.4 in terms of contribution GVA per percentage of employment. For comparison, as shown in Figure 1, Manufacturing is a highly important sector to the EU in terms of employment (15.5% in 2024), however, the GVA contribution is similar at 15.9% providing a ratio of 1.0 for the relative productivity of the sector. The ICT sector is the fourth sector in terms of productivity, narrowly behind Financial and Insurance Activities. As mentioned previously, this doesn't account for the contribution of digital technologies nor the presence of ICT Specialists in the other sectors.

Figure 1. Comparison of the relative contribution of key sectors to the EU27 economy as employment and GVA from largest ratio of GVA to employment

Created with Datawrapper

Source: Elaborated on data provided by Eurostat for 2024. Note: The sector grouping 'Industry (excluding construction)' includes activities like utilities, and with Real Estate should be considered an outlier for size of GVA contribution compared to the number of employees.

Looking forwards, the growth of the ICT sector is very strong both in terms of both GVA and employment. Between 2015-2024 ICT Sector was the top performer – the GVA contribution grew by 65 points and employment by 49 points compared to 2015, see Figure 2. This growth is 5-6 times the average. The nearest sector for GVA was Professional, Scientific, Technical and Administrative which saw a growth of 32 points, 2 times the average. For employment, the nearest sector was Real Estate with 19 points, again double the average.

In this context, 57.5% of EU Enterprises who attempt to hire ICT Specialists report significant difficulties; outside ICT roles, the proportion of employers with difficulties in covering vacancies has doubled since 2015.⁶ Key barriers, however, are not resulting from the cost of salaries but more often to the difficulty in understanding and evaluating the skills of candidates.⁷ These build on the continuous findings of the LEADS and LEADSx2030 teams that the specification of the skills and profiles is becoming ever more challenging as new tools and systems are brought online and the barriers between technical talent and specialists begin to blur.

⁵Asterés (2025) La Dépendance technologique aux softwares & cloud services américains: une estimation des conséquences économiques en Europe

⁶ Manpower (2024) Talent shortage survey

⁷ LEADS Consortium (2023) Final ADS demand and forecast report

Figure 2. Growth in GVA (right) and employment (left) of each sector from 2015-2025 (2015=100)

Source: Elaborated on data provided by Eurostat

1.3 Core definitions of roles and demands

Before entering into the discussion further, it is important to specify what is meant by ICT Specialists and digital roles and provide a clear stratification of needs and demands among skills. As previously established,⁸ the question of what talent should be considered along the following profiles in order of scale of requirements and level of specialisation:

- **A. Inventors**
 - Researchers both in research institutions and companies that are at the forefront of the knowledge of digital technologies and their development.
- **B. Specialists**
 - Professionals who are responsible for the development and implementation of systems and architectures and can provide maintenance, revision and solution of problems through their combined application of theoretical expertise and practical skills
- **C. Experts**
 - Advanced users of the platforms and tools that require development and a level of knowledge of systems, languages and solutions. These ICT Experts are those roles that build solutions and applications to solve a defined challenge or need
- **D. Users**

⁸Rowan, B., Borotis, S., Byrne, J., Fu, N., Moreno Romero, A. M., de Lama, N., Menasalvas, .E., Nielsen, J., & Moreno Navarro, J. J. (2025). Consolidated recommendations for the development of Advanced Digital Skills in Europe.

- Domain experts with limited technical skills for the development of systems or solutions but can manipulate advanced digital tools through defined interfaces.

Formally, the distinction between the profiles A-C is not readily apparent in statistical definitions of ICT Specialists. The current definition is “workers who have the ability to develop, operate and maintain ICT systems, and for whom ICT constitute the main part of their job”. In terms of ISCO-08 Categorisation it encapsulates:

- 133 ICT Service managers.
- 251 Software and applications developers and analysts.
- 252 Database and network professionals.
- 351 ICT operations and user support technicians.
- 352 Telecommunications and broadcasting technicians.
- 2152 Electronic engineers; 2153 Telecommunications engineers; 2166 Graphic and multimedia designers; 2356 Information technology trainers; 2434 ICT sales professionals; 3114 Electronics engineering technicians
- 742 Electronics and telecommunications installers and repairers.

Therefore, it is important for all, to in the context of roles and needs to apply their experience and knowledge to the statistical data to keep in mind the profiles. Recent relevant studies have applied a similar classification to demand,⁹ and for the context of this report, given the umbrella of the Digital Decade Policy Programme, the Profiles B and C are in scope.

From a sectoral perspective, for ICT Professionals and ICT Technicians, the vast majority are employed within the ICT Industry. Beyond this, of note is the role of ICT Specialists in manufacturing and wholesale and retail trade, highlighting the scale of digitalisation of these sectors and the need for in-house digital roles.

Figure 3. Estimated distribution of employed ICT Professionals and ICT Technicians across sectors for 2023

Created with Datawrapper

Source: Elaborated using data from CEDEFOP Skills Intelligence

1.4 Current state-of-play in the labour force

From the latest data, there are over 10.3 million ICT Specialists employed in the EU, a number that has significantly grown over the past decade, from just 6.5 million in 2015. This is a welcome momentum towards the goals of the Digital Decade Policy Programme, although much more is needed to reduce the

⁹ Interface (2025) Solving Europe's AI talent equation: Supply, demand and missing pieces

time to the target goal.¹⁰ When achieved, the goal of 20 million translates into roughly 10% of the current EU labour force employed as ICT Specialists. Such a rate would position the EU as a leader amongst its peers. In relation to other key economies and geographies, the number of ICT Specialists in the EU shows a positive story over the past decade and more. In particular the gap between the EU and the US is narrowing significantly and there is a strong and consistent growth within the EU since 2011, see Figure 4. Latest data from Eurostat from 2024 already places the EU above 5%. The EU27, with 10.3 million is a global powerhouse for ICT roles and jobs, coming second behind Chinese estimates, and ahead of current US reports, at 12.4 and 7.9 million respectively.

Figure 4. Number of employed ICT Specialists as a percentage of total labour force

Source: Elaborated using data from OECD Going Digital Toolkit. Available data is incomplete for most regions after 2018 and some data is different to Eurostat, however, the OECD is retained as the comparable source for relative growth. Some changes not shown for Korea after the application the new ISCO classifications demonstrated a reduction to around 1% after the manufacturing of ICT equipment was isolated.

Figure 5. Total labour force for the period 2000-2025

Source: Elaborated using data from the ILO

More broadly, looking at the evolution of the labour force in general. There is a significant increase in the labour force for India – while over the past decade, the EU and US have experienced a similar trend of growth in the working population, and China has tapered off. In comparison, India is set to continue to grow at a massive rate with an implication for the growing contribution to global number of ICT specialists, in spite of a lower percentage.

Further trends in total population growth show that while growth for India is expected to slow to 0% towards 2040, the rate for the EU is steadily negative towards a rate of -0.5%.

¹⁰ European Commission (2025) State of the Digital Decade 2025

1.4.1 Forecasts and demands to 2035

With the data provided by CEDEFOP, we are able to look at projections beyond 2030 to the next decade from now in terms of occupational demand and replacement.¹¹ In comparison to other occupations both ICT Professionals and ICT Technicians offer a unique position, characterised by a high growth rate with relatively low rate of replacement, see Figure 7 below. This implies that much of the current workforce will still be retained over the next 10 years, and that the ICT Professional and ICT Technician occupations themselves will experience individual dynamics in their growth journey compared to the bulk of other occupations. For these occupations, the investment in talent development and attraction will provide the strongest in terms of ROI for all occupations, with the majority of investments in new talent contributing to the growth demand.

Figure 6. Forecasted growth and replacement rates for defined occupations for period 2022-2035

Source: Elaborated on data provided by CEDEFOP Skills Forecast

In numbers, the net growth by 2035 for both ICT Professionals and ICT Technicians is 1.7 million individuals,¹² replacement requires the training of around 2.5 million existing individuals resulting in a total requirement of 4.2 million gross entrants. For every 1000 net individuals, 2460 amount are required to be trained or recruited in. This compares to occupations such as Health Professionals, where the net growth total is in lower at 1.03 million but due to replacement, the training or recruitment of 5.2 million is needed; for every 1000 net demands, 5021 individuals are required. This demonstrates that for ICT Specialists, the return, in terms of contribution of training and recruitment to growth, the is double that of healthcare professionals, and in fact, across all occupations with positive growth for the period it is the highest ROI, not counting other contributory effects on the economy or spillovers.

¹¹ Replacement refers to the percentage of the current number of individuals currently employed to be lost through retirement or change of occupation

¹² Note that the definition of ICT Specialists is broader than these two occupations – however for ease of interpretation this example is limited to these two principal contributors.

This increase in demand takes place in the context of a declining population but with a marginal growth of 0.3% in the labour force for the EU through to 2035, this signals future challenges as ICT roles will likely remain high in the labour shortages. We do note that positively, the roles of Software Developer, Software Worker and Application Programmer have dropped down the list of top 10 reported shortages in the years 2020-2024, linked to an improvement in supply rather than demand.¹³ In fact, Software Developers have been, behind Waiters and Chefs, one of the highest increases in employment in the years since 2021 (≈19%). This has also been driven by a greater attraction of migrant workers from Third Countries, rather than through supply from within the Single Market itself with roughly 16% of Software Developers coming from outside the EU. This demonstrates a weakness in supply of the talent required to meet the demands of industry, highlighting a dependency.

1.4.2 Key trends in education and supply

There are many a variety of pathways through which ICT Specialists join into the occupations including higher education and vocational and professional training. It is assumed that a significant predictor is the number of graduates of both STEM and ICT from higher education.¹⁴ Both STEM and ICT are necessary leading indicators of future supply; ICT graduates have a direct relationship to the labour market for ICT roles, while STEM is considered to provide a broad basis for the upskilling and training of individual into new ICT roles. This is observed especially in the less defined ICT fields due to the novel nature of the technologies and the constant changing skills pockets.

Figure 7. Comparison of the proportion of graduates (EQF Levels 6-8) within the A STEM and B ICT disciplines for the period 2015-2023

Source: Elaborated using data from Eurostat, OECD and National Statistics Bodies

The EU performs well in the proportion of STEM graduates produced annually (25%), albeit limited in growth. It outperforms the US (23%) and UK (22%), but lags leaders like India and Korea, see Figure 8. In ICT specific disciplines, however, the EU falls to the back of the queue, with the US and UK opening the gap in the past few years (>1.3%), signalling a potential risk to the earlier gains achieved in the employment of ICT Specialists. In fact, the number between the EU and US has widened significantly in the past decade. Through various consultations over the previous years, closing this gap will present a large challenge for Higher Education Institutes; universities are looking to provide attractive offerings but find themselves limited by the access to the top talent in the delivery of the courses and in sourcing the right candidates with the pre-requisite skills levels or experience to enter them.¹⁵

¹³ European Labour Authority (2025) EURES Shortages and surpluses report 2024

¹⁴ Women in Digital Survey 2025 - >65% of respondents (both male and female) held a bachelor's degree or higher in STEM or ICT.

¹⁵ Kavanagh, D. S., Byrne, J., & Thibaudeau, F. (2024). Advanced Digital Skills: Meeting the education and training challenges. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12666047>

2 Advanced Digital Skills Demands

2.1 Definition of demand under skills

While the demand for the number of new ICT Specialists has been previously defined by CEDEFOP, the broad nature of these categorisation of ICT Specialists does not represent the complexity and turbulence that is occurring on a skills and role level. Much of this is driven by the transforming and rapidly progressing of the key technologies in an industrial context. Aside from the omnipresent AI, the focus of LEADSx2030 and the DIGITAL Programme seeks to provide an insight into the skills demands, expressed as skills pockets, across the technology areas of Artificial Intelligence, Automated Systems, Blockchain, Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity, Data Science, Digital Twin, Edge Computing.

The approach to providing such a nuanced demand is outlined in detail in a recent methodological note for the LEADSx2030 data model.¹⁶ Here provides a brief summary of the method for context. The data model leverages a series of libraries that includes job vacancy data, publications, patents and other sources. With this it applies a machine learning approach to provide semantic harmonisation of the text against reference frameworks such as O*NET, ESCO and the previously used LEADS taxonomy to provide a clustering and nearest neighbour analysis of skills and key words. Through graph-based representations and contextual co-occurrence, allowing for consistent and comparable analysis across diverse domains, the analytical unit of the skills pocket is defined. A skills pocket is a collection of clustered skills key words that have a close relationship through a minimum number of appearances.

From here, the analysis of skills is applied to the roles and the definition of the skills pockets across them, providing a rich view on the skills demands from industry across the scope technology areas. This model is continuously being reviewed, and in the next annual report, we look forward to analysing how the skills pockets themselves evolve. The resulting data is available publicly through the demand dashboard.¹⁷

Moving from relative to quantified

Through the analysis of the jobs vacancy data, we are able to extract the skills pockets. However, to be able to quantify the number of profiles required against these skills pockets and technology areas¹⁸, we must first establish the total demand for the year in analysis. Presently, we estimate that there are just under 5 million job vacancies present in the EU27. The provided vacancy rate of 2.2% for the EU labour force. The Eurostat and ILO defined total labour force are figures of 197 million (Eurostat) or 221 million (ILO). The number in employment represents then 97.8% of the total positions present, providing an estimate of between 4.5 and 5.0 million open vacancies.

Within our libraries we have analysed 3 million unique job advertisements from across the EU27. Of these around 200,000 met criteria for classification as digital roles, scaling up to total vacancies we estimate the total number of vacancies in 2025 for ICT Specialists to be at roughly 420,000 positions in the EU27.

A note on the use of Open Job Advertisements (OJA)

Over recent years, the leveraging of online vacancies and the mining of the data within has been adopted by a greater number of actors in the attempt to provide skills intelligence for a variety of purposes, chief among them policy development and training and education anticipation.^{19,20} Many interesting studies and analyses have been performed on the datasets with providers like Lightcast providing aggregate sets and

¹⁶ Ketamo, H., Passi-Rauste, A., Pesic, I., & Andres Felipe, Z. P. (2025). D1.1 Advanced Digital Skills Data Model. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17414186>

¹⁷ <https://advancedskills.eu/ads-demand-dashboard-2025/>

¹⁸ For the data mapping and analysis, job postings are classified by technology areas prior to skills pocket analysis based on job titles and descriptions through the presence of 2 or more matching keywords.

¹⁹ Sostero, M. and Fernandez Macias, E., (2021) The professional lens: what online job advertisements can say about occupational task profiles, European Commission, JRC125917.

²⁰ Charmanas, K.; Georgiou,

K.; Mittas, N.; Angelis, L. (2025) Digital Requirements for Systems Analysts in Europe: A Sectoral Analysis of Online Job Advertisements and ESCO Skills. Information 2025, 16, 363. <https://doi.org/10.3390/info16050363>

advances in the use of skills-first competency frameworks and the deployment of data spaces provide relevance for growth and improvements in the use of such data.²¹

While many benefits can be extracted, it is important to acknowledge some of the potential limitations. The use of OJA inserts a series of biases that are relevant. Firstly, they tend to represent high-skilled jobs and professions that limits the application in certain occupational studies, fortunately for ICT Specialists this is not the case. Secondly, there is a variation in the representation across different countries and geographies that limits the direct application on a country-by-country level. Thirdly, it is estimated that the majority of job adverts are for replacement rather than new roles, some estimates of around 90%, which limits the projection of new profiles but on a skills level should demonstrate the evolving roles. Finally, the lag present between when a skills need emerges, is translated into a job description and is routinely integrated into job postings means that OJA based analyses can show us a snapshot of the market of between 6-18 months in the past.

Taking these into account, the LEADSx2030 data model provides a valuable assessment on the relative developments of skills demands and the rapidly evolving nature of the profiles and requirements.

2.2 Demand across tech areas

Overall demand for ICT Specialist job postings appears to have dropped significantly for the period between 2021 and 2025. This is in line with expectations due to the change in the global hiring practices of digital roles. It is commonly reported that there was a peak in hiring of digital talent globally that was reached in 2022 with market corrections taking place in the years since and remaining steady from 2024. Net numbers, over a longer period are still higher than previous baselines. This is seen in Eurostat figures where the relative number of job postings for ICT roles online went from nearly 10% of the total in 2022 to 7% in 2025.²²

From the LEADSx2030 data, taking a relative view, the top technology profiles in demand still indicates that Data Science and Cybersecurity are the largest portion of profiles being sought. As shown in Figure 9, the range of demand for profiles in 2025 is small between technology areas between 115,000 and 101,600 for the major technology areas. Automated Systems and Edge Computing are lower in range at 83,000 and 76,000 respectively, see Figure 10.

Figure 8. Estimated number of vacancies per technology area 2021-2025 - reduced scope

Source: LEADSx2030. Technology areas Automated Systems and Edge Computing have been omitted for clarity, see further figures for details.

²¹ OECD (2025), Empowering the Workforce in the Context of a Skills-First Approach, OECD Skills Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/345b6528-en>.

²² Eurostat 2025 ISOC_SK_OJA1

Of note is the resilient demand for Internet of Things and Blockchain, it has been previously reported that the convergence in Edge computing and the application of AI managed systems would predict an increase in Cloud profiles dominating these fields.²³ However our data places Cloud profiles behind these areas.

Figure 9. Observed demand trends across each technology area for period 2021-2025

Created with Datawrapper

Source: LEADSx2030

Across the technology areas, in terms of skills pockets, Data, AI and Cyber have the largest number of skills pockets associated with their profiles. As can be seen from Figure 11, when considering the relative distribution between the skills pockets under the areas, however, Blockchain and Digital Twins have a high number of skills pockets and with less even demand between them compared to the larger tech areas.

To compare the overlaps and synergistic nature between the individual technology areas, a mapping of the top ten skills pockets in present in each area for 2025 is provided in Table 1 below. As anticipated, Cloud provides a clustering around the profiles of Digital Twin and Edge Computing as well as Robotics, but fewer crossovers are identified with AI or Cyber. As will be demonstrated in further sections, there is, however, a significant contribution of Cloud related skills pockets in each of the technology areas.

On the other end of the spectrum, AI, Cyber and Data individually share fewer skills pockets with other technology areas, although the latter two appear to be more broadly relevant. A significant anomaly appears to be the coupling of AI profiles with IoT over other areas.

Figure 10. Comparison of the diversity of skills pockets under tech areas as distribution of demand for each pocket vs number present

²³ Jones, S., Rowan, B., Pourabdollahian, G. (2023). On the Edge: Marking the impact of the CEI continuum on skills demands.

Figure 11. Overlap among the top 10 skills pockets per technology area 2025

	AI	Automated Systems	Blockchain	Cloud	Cyber	Data	Digital Twin	Edge Computing	IoT	Robotics	
AI		3	4	4	3	3	4	3	6	3	33
Automated Systems	3		6	4	2	1	4	4	3	5	32
Blockchain	4	6		6	4	4	7	6	6	5	48
Cloud	4	4	6		4	4	8	8	6	7	51
Cyber	3	2	4	4		5	3	4	4	4	33
Data	3	1	4	4	5		5	5	4	4	35
Digital Twin	4	4	7	8	3	5		7	6	6	50
Edge Computing	3	4	6	8	4	5	7		5	7	49
IoT	6	3	6	6	4	4	6	5		6	46
Robotics	3	5	5	7	4	4	6	7	6		47
	33	32	48	51	33	35	50	49	46	47	

Source: LEADSx2030

2.3 Skills pockets demands

Taking the skills pocket trends as whole, i.e. across all technology areas, the relative positioning of the demand for individual skills pockets is highly dynamic and is anticipated to be so as we continue to experience both the greater deployment of novel AI underpinned systems, the on streaming of new tools and platforms and the accelerated convergence between technology areas as previously reported. The shift in rankings has ranged from a drop in 21 places for Quality Assurance (from 22nd to 33rd) and a rise in 18 places for Cloud Security (From 40th to 22nd). As shown in Table 2, there is a notable trend for the increase in security and security solutions with a corresponding drop for the more infrastructure and less engineering-based skills pockets. Such examples including testing, UX, knowledge and applications. There is a notable requirement, in addition to security for data management and governance skills.

Such shifts over the past two years towards security and data management demonstrates the cross-technology dependency on such skills pockets. While Systems Engineering and Software Development rise, Programming itself has fallen. Given the current popular dialogue around the reduced need for coding through deployment of Generative AI solutions, this has not yet translated into new job descriptions. Across all technology areas, there is a greater presence of Information Systems which as a skills pocket is a catch all, perhaps indicating that generic IT skills are being referenced as industries seek to define these new emerging skillsets.

Table 1. List of skills pockets ranked in order of demand for 2025 with difference relative to 2023 position

Skills Pocket	Rank	2025	Skills Pocket	Rank	2025
Information Security	1 (2)	58977	Systems Integration	23 (-5)	24961
Data Protection	2 (0)	56656	Data Architecture	24 (4)	24830
Data Analytics	3 (-2)	54864	Cloud Technologies	25 (-6)	24654
Information Systems	4 (7)	52397	Knowledge Management	26 (-6)	22213
Data Engineering	5 (0)	46294	Cloud Infrastructure	27 (-3)	22122
Business Analytics	6 (11)	43637	Network Security	28 (8)	21604
Data Management	7 (-3)	38428	Systems Design	29 (10)	19793
Programming	8 (-2)	34549	Technology Management	30 (-8)	19737
Systems Engineering	9 (17)	33394	Data Security	31 (2)	19388
Software Development	10 (4)	32650	Software Testing	32 (0)	18580
Cloud Services	11 (2)	32282	Quality Assurance	33 (-21)	17287
Experience Design	12 (9)	32215	Test Automation	34 (0)	16621
DevOps	13 (-5)	31416	Digital Transformation	35 (7)	15498
Business Technologies	14 (-5)	31199	SAP/ERP	36 (7)	14982
Machine Learning	15 (12)	31102	User Experience	37 (0)	14657
Agile Methodology	16 (7)	30693	Web Services	38 (-13)	14563
Security Management	17 (12)	30535	System Testing	39 (-8)	13570
AI and BI Tools	18 (-8)	30462	Interface Design	40 (-5)	11088
Business Software	19 (-12)	30192	Process Automation	41 (0)	11020
Software Engineering	20 (-4)	30066	Distributed Systems	42 (-4)	7542
IT Infrastructure	21 (-6)	27277	Power Engineering	43 (1)	5580
Cloud Security	22 (18)	26000	Digital Media	44 (-14)	5398

2.4 Demand signals under top technology areas

2.4.1 AI

Currently for AI, there is a significant demand for general IT skills under Information Systems, this is experiencing both a high-growth and high demand that would indicate a frothiness to the definition of an AI specialist. The relative shift over the past few years towards data, systems and security away from more cloud based and programming demands mirrors similar observations.

The shift in foundational skills focused on moving from traditional machine learning (e.g., model building and training) to strategic foundational generative model orchestration and leveraging advanced, pre-trained, and agent-driven AI technologies in practical applications.²⁴ That said, there is still a steady demand for Software Development and Software Engineering, for now. Compared to Data Science, for example, the increasing importance and demand of DevOps for AI may reflect the shift in AI profiles from more fundamental systems development into a production and operational contexts, implying the move of AI profiles up the production chain.

Figure 12. Mapping of AI skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

Table 2. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for AI for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Security Management	279%	Interface Design	-31%
Business Analytics	267%	Knowledge Management	-32%
Systems Design	194%	Cloud Infrastructure	-39%
Information Systems	183%	Process Automation	-43%
Information Security	146%	Software Testing	-50%
Network Security	139%	Cloud Technologies	-50%
Devops	135%	Distributed Systems	-51%
Data Engineering	107%	Systems Integration	-53%
Software Engineering	105%	User Experience	-66%
Agile Methodology	91%	Programming	-66%

Source: LEADSx2030

²⁴ AI Workforce Consortium (2025), ICT in Motion: The Next Wave of AI Integration

2.4.2 Data Science

In general, demand for Data Science roles, which includes engineers, analysts and scientists among others, are coming down in demand significantly from the highs of the beginning of this decade. What may appear to be a significant decline, does not recognise the diffusion of the skills pockets across the other technology areas, like with cybersecurity. At the same time, it is reasonable to assume that many roles that would have been classified under data science a few years ago, may now be classified under areas like AI.²⁵

The general trends demonstrate a data role that is transitioning rapidly from what was a steady defined profile towards those that are highly integrated with AI and generative AI solutions, marrying the access to off-the-shelf models and solutions with demand for data integrity and security across IT systems.

For these profiles, Data Analytics and Programming are declining in importance but remain the core basis of such profiles along with the use of Cloud Infrastructure. This means the foundational and more technical skillset required, although this looks to be evolving when considering the declining skills pockets. The range of growth and decline for the skills pockets is moderate with security and compliance retaining growth. The decline of UX and DevOps may indicate, in contrast to the AI roles, a descent down the production chain for data specialists and a move from the push operations, perhaps transitioning into the CIO/CISO units.

Figure 13. Mapping of Data Science skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

Table 3. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for Data Science for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Information Security	31%	Cloud Technologies	-76%
Data Protection	16%	Digital Media	-78%
Business Analytics	10%	Systems Integration	-81%
Cloud Security	0%	Security Management	-82%
Business Software	-3%	Test Automation	-84%
Cloud Infrastructure	-5%	Machine Learning	-85%
Data Security	-11%	User Experience	-86%
AI and BI Tools	-15%	SAP/ERP	-93%
Data Architecture	-23%	DevOps	-95%
Agile Methodology	-29%	Distributed Systems	-100%

²⁵ Kavargyris, D.C.; Georgiou, K.; Papaioannou, E.; Moysiadis, T.; Mittas, N.; Angelis, L. Future Skills in the GenAI Era: A Labor Market Classification System Using Kolmogorov–Arnold Networks and Explainable AI. Algorithms 2025, 18, 554. <https://doi.org/10.3390/a18090554>

2.4.3 Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity skills pockets are present across all the technology areas, for security profiles specifically there is a strong consistent growth for skills pockets, second only to AI for the positive growth across the top 10 pockets. There is a stability to these role present, with a consistent demand for systems management and security operations.

Figure 14. Mapping of Cybersecurity skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

Created with Datawrapper

In terms of declines, there is a possible trend towards the application of new platforms and tools as evidenced by the drop in importance for specific software and ERPs more generally and a corresponding decline in the need for interfaces and UX.

This also may explain the declining importance of software engineering to these roles. On the other hand, while UX and UI are on the decline, the broad category of Experience Design in present, itself composed of skills like System Knowledge, Data Analysis, etc. compared to the more design and programming nature of the previous two skills pockets.

The continued relevance of cloud platforms for cyber profiles is in contrast with other technology areas and generally the infrastructure

components is less of a demand, likely due to the orchestration of the systems or a continued trend in a greater specialisation of the roles.²⁶

Table 4. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for Cybersecurity for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Security Management	239%	Software Engineering	-26%
Network Security	217%	Technology Management	-28%
Cloud Technologies	170%	Process Automation	-31%
Experience Design	136%	Business Software	-35%
Information Systems	69%	SAP/ERP	-37%
Cloud Services	54%	Test Automation	-46%
Systems Engineering	53%	User Experience	-53%
Web Services	46%	Data Security	-57%
Business Analytics	43%	Interface Design	-63%
Data Management	37%	Programming	-90%

²⁶ OECD (2024), Building a Skilled Cyber Security Workforce in Europe: Insights from France, Germany and Poland, OECD Skills Studies, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/3673cd60-en>.

2.4.4 Internet of Things

For IoT, the decline from 2021 was sharp but not as sharp as would have been anticipated, this may be due to the slower adoption of edge computing systems, retaining device management and platform roles over the convergence with cloud. Added to this is the relative immaturity in the market for IoT solutions; end points are expected to account for 46% of the total 156bn EUR Cloud-Edge-IoT market over the next four years.²⁷ Another contributing factor could be the continued digitalisation of the physical infrastructure, particularly in sectors like utilities and energy where IoT skills are providing moderate demand.²⁸

There is, like with data, a broad decline across skills pocket growth but a consistent steady set of skills pockets define these roles. These are Software Engineering, Cloud Technologies, DevOps, etc. There is a notable absence for the over hardware skills that, due to the deployment of greater orchestration platforms and virtualisation of devices and systems, will be reduced as the IoT specialist moves to a more virtual deployment context.

Security is by far the strongest need for IoT roles, with a continued demand as IT systems increase in complexity away from single/dual location cloud paradigms. Though there is a noticeable specific decline in importance and demand for both network and cloud security, most likely, as with data roles, greater adoption of microservices and meta operation systems and solutions.

Figure 15. Mapping of IoT skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

Table 5. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for IoT for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Security Management	55%	Network Security	-73%
Data Architecture	-19%	Data Protection	-81%
Information Security	-20%	Interface Design	-82%
Agile Methodology	-20%	Cloud Security	-83%
Information Systems	-26%	Digital Transformation	-86%
Systems Engineering	-27%	Test Automation	-86%
Data Engineering	-31%	User Experience	-87%
Experience Design	-32%	Process Automation	-87%
Devops	-33%	Web Services	-89%
Business Technologies	-33%	Digital Media	-92%

²⁷ CEI Sphere (2025) Preliminary Market Analysis for the Cloud-Edge-IoT

²⁸ European Commission (2025) Upskilling needs for the energy system to support the energy transition with a focus on digital skills – ETIP SNET WG4, digitalisation of the electricity system, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2926/6953671>

2.4.5 Robotics

The general demand pattern for Robotics has seen a decline across the past four years, but this in reverse for the past two years. The generic pocket of Information Systems (not shown in the figure) is the only shift in this trend, signalling uncertainty in the definition of the skills demanded currently. Robotics and autonomous systems are presumed to increase the demand for programming and systems thinking, skills crucial for managing and optimising interactions with autonomous technology.²⁹

Figure 16. Mapping of Robotics skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

The data while still backing this, through the consistent high level of demand, does show a slower growth rate for technical and foundational skills such as Programming, Software Development and Engineering, Test Automation, etc.

The robotics field is undergoing a marked transformation, moving away from traditional IT and routine automation skills towards higher-level, integrative, or cross-disciplinary capabilities.

The data may suggest an automation or maturation of many previously in-demand skills (like Programming and Cloud Services), possibly through low-code /no-code platforms, extensive automation, or new technologies that reduce

dependency on specialised expertise. It must also be mentioned that the global positioning of the EU capacities in industrial robotics is a key competitive strength compared to other global regions and the decline of specific skills pockets for these roles should be of importance for planned investments.

Table 6. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for Robotics for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Information Systems	68%	Software Development/Engineering	-67%
Software Testing	-13%	Test Automation	-67%
Data Management	-19%	Power Engineering	-69%
IT Infrastructure	-20%	Cloud Technologies	-72%
Agile Methodology	-21%	Cloud Services	-77%
Experience Design	-32%	Knowledge Management	-79%
Cloud Infrastructure	-36%	Devops	-86%
Digital Transformation	-36%	Process Automation	-88%
Quality Assurance	-40%	Security Management	-91%
Programming	-49%	Digital Media	-94%

²⁹ World Economic Forum (2025) Future of Jobs Report 2025

2.4.6 Cloud

The low demand for Cloud Computing roles compared to areas like IoT and Robotics is not clearly understood, it may be that given the relevance of cloud-based skills across the other technology areas, the distinct Cloud roles are less prevalent as a standalone profile. This is in contrast with reports of the high demands for roles such as Cloud Engineers, the massive penetration of public cloud into operations and the dependency of cloud integration for deployment of other technologies and systems.³⁰

The picture for Cloud roles is one of large polarisation; Security Management has surged by 282%, and Network Security by 234%, representing the fastest-growing skill areas in the cloud domain. This aligns with industry trends showing that 61% of organisations cite security and compliance as primary barriers to cloud adoption, while 76% report shortages in cloud security expertise.³¹

One unique trend here is the continued relevance for ERP skills pockets that has not been conserved for the other technology areas.

In general, it can be surmised that the Cloud roles are moving away from demand for systems builders and into more deployment and optimisation.

Figure 17. Mapping of Cloud skills pockets demands in 2025 against the growth for period 2021-2025

Table 7. Top 10 and bottom 10 trending skills pockets for Cloud for period 2021-2025

Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025	Skills Pocket	Δ 2021-2025
Security Management	282%	Data Management	-63%
Network Security	234%	Information Security	-64%
Information Systems	191%	Experience Design	-66%
SAP/ERP	13%	Business Software	-69%
IT Infrastructure	-2%	Distributed Systems	-69%
User Experience	-28%	Systems Integration	-72%
Data Analytics	-33%	Software Testing	-79%
Web Services	-34%	Systems Design	-83%
Knowledge Management	-39%	Test Automation	-85%
Cloud Infrastructure	-40%	Data Security	-90%

³⁰ AI Workforce Consortium (2025), ICT in Motion: The Next Wave of AI Integration

³¹ Thales (2025) Cloud Security Study

3 Broader reflection on general trends and observations

3.1 Shifting nature of work

What the future of work looks like is a broad point of discussion, much research has been conducted, and much opinion is currently being assessed in the context of the large-scale investments in generative AI capacity by firms across the globe. The current experience of digitisation has led to a profound transformation in the nature and organisation of work, primarily by introducing necessary standardisation and centralisation of information flows. While this process has reduced labour input in routine clerical tasks, it has simultaneously resulted in the routinisation of work within many non-routine professional roles as they become subject to rigid, digitally controlled procedures.³²

Looking forward to 2030, the immediate future of work is heavily shaped by technological advancements, particularly broadening digital access (expected to transform 60% of businesses) and AI and information processing technologies (anticipated to transform 86% of businesses). The balance of task execution is rapidly moving towards human-machine collaboration, with work tasks expected to be nearly evenly split across humans alone, technology alone, and augmented collaboration by 2030. This augmentation focus means technologies like Generative AI are expected to enhance human core skills and equip specialized roles, such as Doctors and Engineers, with forefront knowledge to solve complex problems, driving strong anticipated growth in demand for skills like AI and big data, networks and cybersecurity, and technological literacy

It has been observed that the nature of automation and augmentation is not a binary situation but that can evolve from one to another and vice versa. An analysis of the users of Claude, has shown that augmentation is the dominant trend for GenAI deployments among professional and technical occupation classes having started from an automation position.³³ The material impact on work is not universal though, early signals from the US demonstrate the negative impact AI investment is having on the job prospects of early career individuals in terms of both employment and salaries, especially for software developers with high exposure to automation effects. While conversely, middle-to-senior career level prospects have continued to grow.³⁴

3.2 AI is not AI

From our own data alone, it is evident that the deployment of AI both as an application (i.e. GenAI) but also as a key enabler in the management and orchestration of tools and systems, can explain changing demands for skills pockets. Zooming out on the global current competitive landscape for AI, part will be defined by the physical (data centres, energy markets and chips), the other part is through the supply of the professionals who can support its adoption.³⁵

AI is an evolution of previous technologies and therefore so too are AI profiles. There is significant demand for skills related to data management, cybersecurity, systems engineering and software. These pockets in general will not disappear but act as the core what is required for AI deployment professionals. The evolution may be accelerated through the application of these new tools, and the paradoxical or polarising reskilling or deskilling of tasks and roles in ICT Specialists will continue to be a characteristic of these occupations. What remains important, is to understand that AI needs experts in data security, in cloud system integrations, in architecture decision and in governance and privacy. It can be seen as a clustering from existing talent pools but is not a single novel discipline.

Recent experience with Data Scientists saw a glut of supply through bootcamps, master's programmes, training courses, etc. These profiles, equipped with the technical skills for programming and use of advanced applications led to high expectations from industry. The experience, however, found that instead

³² Fernandez Macias, E., Gonzalez Vazquez, I., Torrejon Perez, S. and Nurski, L., Work in the Digital Era: How Technology is Transforming Work and Occupations, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2025, https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/0956105_JRC141451

³³ Handa, K. et al (2025) Which Economic Tasks are Performed with AI? Evidence from Millions of Claude Conversations

³⁴ Brynjolfsson, E. et al (2025) Canaries in the Coal Mine? Six Facts about the Recent Employment Effects of Artificial Intelligence

³⁵ See Apply AI Strategy

of applying machine learning and building specific models, majority of effort was dedicated to data cleaning and integrations. Parallels should be drawn to the needed roles for AI to ensure that expectations are well aligned and met between the education and training community and employers.

3.3 Open or closed profiles

One of the dominant features of the ICT market for the past decade has been the increased centralisation of whole ecosystems on individual vendors; AWS, Microsoft and Google account for 70% of the EU market.³⁶ While vendor lock-in is not a new phenomenon, the increasing role of talent and ICT platform specialisation can play a significant role. Certification of training and standardisation in specific ecosystems has benefits for companies and individuals in both demonstrating and validating their skills, but also beds in longer-term stickiness and barrier to change. This is analogous to the Boeing/Airbus purchasing decisions by airlines led by costs of pilot retraining.

As a purely illustrative example, a brief sampling of publicly available training programmes³⁷ found a different picture for many of the technology areas in terms of the readily available generic or neutral courses versus vendor specific. As shown in the figure on the right, there was a significant difference of vendor specific courses in the programme. In terms of the dominant players the following were identified: Cloud Computing - AWS, Microsoft, Google; Networking – Cisco, IoT – Cisco, AWS, Microsoft. Data – IBM, Robotics – various including ABB, KUKA, DENSO, Kawasaki, Universal Robot; Cyber – Cisco.

Figure 18. Number of vendor specific or generic training programmes found for selected technology areas

Created with Datawrapper

Source: LEADSx2030 based on AI enabled web search

Of course, IT vendors have always required to support customers and clients in the training and development of the skills for the deployment of their technologies, and it is a necessary part of supporting a healthy ecosystem. The risk appears, however, when the market itself is not dynamic or competitive.

³⁶ Synergy Research Group (2025)

³⁷ Using Perplexity Deep Research 200 programmes were scanned by web search for 8 EU countries and a final 78 were reviewed in detail. Programmes were categorised as either vendor-specific (tied to particular technology platforms/ecosystems) or generic/vendor-neutral (teaching universal concepts applicable across platforms).

4 EU Investments in ADS supply – ADS SO4 Cluster

In terms of Advanced Digital Skills, the DIGITAL programme’s Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) states:

“Advanced Digital Skills shall support the development of Advanced Digital Skills in areas covered by the Programme in order to contribute to increasing Europe’s talent pool, bridge the digital divide and foster greater professionalism, especially with regard to high performance and cloud computing, big data analytics, cybersecurity, distributed ledger technologies, quantum technologies, robotics, artificial intelligence, while taking gender balance into account.”³⁸

Under the SO4 there is an extensive portfolio to date of 55 initiatives focused on the delivery of new advanced digital skills programmes. These include specialised master’s programmes and courses, short-term training courses, a cybersecurity skills academy, programmes for reinforcing skills in semiconductors, and a EuroHPC training platform for high-performance computing.

Table 8. Types and scale of actions in the SO4 Cluster

Topic code	No.	Duration	EU funding	Total ³⁹
Specialised education programmes and courses in key capacity areas				
DIGITAL-2021-SKILLS-01-SPECIALISED	8	2022-2026	€56.5M	€103M
DIGITAL-2022-SKILLS-03-SPECIALISED-EDU	12	2023-2027	€78.2M	€125.5M
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-05-SPECIALISED-EDU	5	2024-2029	€32.6M	€35.3M
DIGITAL-2024-ADVANCED-DIGITAL-07-KEYCAPACITY	9	2025-2029	€52.5M	€59.6M
Short-term training courses in key capacity areas				
DIGITAL-2022-TRAINING-02-SHORT-COURSES	12	2022-2025	€24.3M	€40.5M
Cybersecurity skills academy				
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-05-CYBERACADEMY	5	2024-2027	€11.7M	€22.8M
Reinforcing skills in semiconductors				
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-04-CHIPS	2	2024-2028	€9.1M	€18.3M
EuroHPC training platform				
DIGITAL-EUROHPC-JU-2022-TRAINING-02	1	2024-2025	€2M	€2M
Boosting digital skills of young pupils and girls				
DIGITAL-2023-SKILLS-04-BOOSTINGDIGIT	1	2024-2026	€6M	€6M
Total	55	2022-2029	€272.9M	€413M

The main target areas, for which these programmes aim to improve the supply of advanced digital skills, include cybersecurity, Artificial Intelligence (AI), manufacturing and infrastructure, business innovation, SMEs and digital health. Other notable areas are energy and sustainability, public administration, and semiconductors.

The main technology areas covered by the funded projects is visualised in Figure 27 below. The mapping has been validated by the project coordinators, in the context of preparing the first version of the DIGITAL Projects Brochure.⁴⁰ This does not include projects not yet featured on the specific version of the brochure, such as the SPECIALISED 2025, for which the information has been collected directly from the project websites or other available online sources.

³⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec/2022/2481/oj>

³⁹ These numbers account for the total EU-funding requested and the total investment including co-funding from other sources and private investment.

⁴⁰ <https://zenodo.org/records/15056357>

According to Figure 27, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Cybersecurity remain core topics of old and new courses, followed by Data & analytics, Blockchain and IoT. Cybersecurity received an additional boost through the Cybersecurity Skills Academy call, which explicitly guided the contents of the submitted project proposals. Meanwhile, Virtual Reality (VR), including Augmented Reality and Extended Reality (XR), appears to be gaining prominence as a major area of interest within the cluster, with four out of nine projects funded in 2025 incorporating it into their curriculum design. On the other hand, technology areas, such as Robotics, Cloud-Edge, Chip design and Microelectronics, have not been addressed at all by the latest funding calls in 2023 and 2025.

Figure 19. Mapping of supply against technology areas

Source: LEADSx2030

About LEADSx2030

LEADSx2030 is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) funded under the Advanced Digital Skills Strategic Objective 4 (SO4) of the DIGITAL Programme. As a CSA, it is tasked with:

- Delivering insights into the changing advanced digital skills demands in the EU, and determining to what extent the current education and training offers match the needs of the current and future labour market.
- Recommending priority areas for new funding programmes and giving indications on which type of programmes and training is most effective for building up advanced digital skills.
- Supporting excellence in education and training institutions, aiming at the development of a dynamic digital education and training ecosystem.
- Promoting collaboration among the SO4 Cluster, i.e. the consortia awarded from the different call topics under the DIGITAL SO4.

As such, over a period of 48 months LEADSx2030 will:

- Provide a continuous review of demand and supply changes related to advanced digital skills.
- Map the outputs of the SO4 Cluster to identify key results and success stories.
- Develop the SO4 Cluster into a dynamic network.
- Provide opportunities for synergies with relevant European actors.
- Bring all stakeholders together in point-of-reference annual advanced digital skills summits.
- Support the strategic EU policy objectives through targeted analyses and recommendations.

In this context, the Best Practice Library (D3.1) is an example of a tool developed by LEADSx2030 to support the development of the SO4 Cluster into a dynamic network, through the dissemination of success stories, exchange of knowledge and promotion of synergies.

Latest information about the initiative can be found at www.advancedskills.eu.